

It's a Bird...It's a Plane.... No, it's Sicodinet: a Blended-Learning Experience in Management Accounting in the University of León

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Abstract. Information and Communication Technologies have involved new possibilities and changes in the teaching-learning process. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to explain an education innovation, Sicodinet, which is a Blended-learning experience developed in the "Cost and Management Accounting" profile in the University of León. Therefore, first this work expounds the context of the project and the process and requirements for choosing the digital platform. Next, the Sicodinet contents and tools are explained; and before the conclusions, the users' evaluation is shown. This project has involved a great support for students and has helped them to build their knowledge.

Keywords: Blended-Learning, Virtual Learning Space, students' support, knowledge communities, social constructionist pedagogy

1 Introduction

Higher Education is going through a new process owing to the introduction of Communication and Information Technologies (ICT). This fact means a significant change in higher teaching and learning because it makes easy the creation of social communication spaces.

The use of ICT in education has undergone several phases, as Fig. 1 shows, which have involved an increase of their complexity and have improved their benefits.

Blended-Learning, the last phase that Fig. 1 shows, has involved a support for traditional teaching because it has improved the ICT advantages, at the same time that teachers assume their traditional role in face to face teaching.

This work is about a B-Learning experience which has developed its on-line training by means of a Virtual Learning Space (VLS) so-called "Control and Management Information Systems in Telematics Environments (Sicodinet)" (<http://sicodinet.unileon.es>). Its aims are to support the traditional teaching and to progress in the application of emergent technologies to education in order to facilitate the new design of subjects related to the "Cost and Management Accounting" teaching profile in the University of León (Spain).

Fig. 1. Development of the ICT in teaching- learning process.

Therefore, the Sicodinet background is explained firstly and then, the process for choosing the platform in which the project has been implemented is expounded in the third part of the paper. The fourth part explains the innovation experience and the different contents of a Sicodinet course, by differentiating the general and the specific ones. Next, the results of the users' evaluation are shown and finally we finish the paper with the conclusions.

2 Sicodinet VLS Background

Sicodinet is a project which has a main objective; making a new learning design to adapt the traditional teaching techniques to the new Information Society.

The start-up and development of Sicodinet has involved that, on the one hand, a big amount of students and teachers can access to the VLS and, on the other hand, the necessity of coordinate the subjects of the teaching profile in order to students can follow the traditional and the on-line teachings. Moreover, the VLS has been used as a complement in PhD courses, to performance virtual workshop in conferences and to give on-line seminars.

Because of these, the project has tried to get both purposes by choosing tools that allow, on the one hand, the support for traditional teaching and its methodology and, on the other hand, the administrative and teaching management of subjects and students. The second perspective is very important because the VLS has been provided with enough dynamism to avoid being only on-line materials. It promotes students' participation, speeds up tuition process, goes up practical aspects and, finally, the VLS allows students to manage administrative process.

According to our objectives, we can differentiate two important aspects in the methodology to develop Sicodinet: conceptual base and technical base of the project. The phases of the project have simultaneously coordinated both bases (conceptual concepts and the technical performance).

One of the most important phases to develop the technical base of the project was the "Initial phase" because the platform where the project would be implemented had to be chosen. Therefore, the choice of the platform is studying in the next section of the paper.

3 Initial Analysis and Choice of the Digital Platform

Before choosing the digital platform to develop the technical base of the project, the current and future services which we want to give to the potential users were analyzed in order to choose the most suitable technological tools. Nowadays there are a lot of teleteaching platforms, so we analyzed different options, by considering the main objectives and the available means to its implementation and its maintenance.

For this reason, the main effort was to analyse the different platforms because our platform should facilitate the update and have the next resources:

- Resources which allow communication
- Resources for following the students' progress
- Resources for students' management
- Resources which make easy collaborative work
- Resources for accessing to the learning information and contents
- Resources which allow creating evaluation and auto evaluation activities.

Therefore, we looked for platforms which follow our requests and functions. Firstly, we analyzed several comparative researches about different platforms¹. After this, we analyzed and applied some examples in many platforms². Finally, the technical base of the project has been developed in the Moodle platform³ because it is free software which allows carrying out the teaching and the administrative part of the project and has technical, operative and legal advantages. It is also impossible to implement a project like this one by using owner software because Sicodinet VLS is developed by few teachers. Moreover, owner software involves high buying and licence costs for updating.

In addition to these previous requirements, we have considered other ones; *Educational Flexibility* because, even though the main aim is to complete traditional teaching, our platform should be a useful tool to face the different types of teaching; *Usability*, it means that the system must be effective regarding its easy use, and people who are used to utilizing applications as for example e-mail, the Internet or forums can use the platform intuitively; *Technological Flexibility* because the project promoters are the managers of the VLS, so the easiness to change technical aspects is an important request to choose our platform; *Accessibility* because the users should access to the information although some of them have any mental or physical handicap and we should also consider accessibility in general, as the good access to the VLS; *Future Developments* because it is important to know the commitment of the developers and the users to keep and develop our platform in the future. Therefore, as well as we considered the different modules, contents, tools, implementation easiness, etc. of the platforms, we also pay attention to the communities which carry out the development and update.

¹ The researches can be look up in the next web pages: <http://www.gate.upm.es>; http://www.elearning.com/modules.php?name=Web_Links&f_op=viewlink&cid=32; <http://edutools.info/course/compare/>; http://cent.uji.es/doc/eveauji_es.pdf; <http://campusvirtual.uma.es/ieev/filos.htm>

² Manhattan Virtual Classroom (<http://manhattan.sourceforge.net>), Miguel (<http://hidrogeno.unileon.es/miguel>), Claroline (<http://www.claroline.net>), etc

³ <http://moodle.org>

4 Sicodinet Project: an Innovation University Experience

In this section we are going to specify the current proposal which is developing at the moment so that the Virtual Learning Space contents can be described. The initial page to access to Sicodinet is shown in Fig. 2.

But before analysing the contents of Sicodinet, we want to emphasize our "Citizen's Charter" which all the participants can see. Although it is not compulsory for us, a Citizen's Charter has been developed because we are part of Civil Service and the VLS users should know our principles and commitments and their rights. So, this letter reflects the commitment which the teachers in charge of Sicodinet have assumed, the quality academic indicators, a proposal for Sicodinet users' suggestions, complaints or incidents and, finally the letter also reflects our performance principles and values. The aim of the letter is to increase the excellence of the academic activity in order to improve Sicodinet continuously. It does not mean that we want to treat our students as customers, but we think student is the main character in the learning process. So, we want to get a better and more proactive teacher-student relationship than just customer-supplier relationship.

Nevertheless, because we are a Civil Service, we also give interesting information for students (groups, timetables, exams, etc) and our commitment to follow it ethically and, finally, the quality indicators which the University of León try to ensure to students.

4.1 Access to the Virtual Learning Space Sicodinet

As we have expounded before, the VLS has been developed by considering each of the subjects related to the "Cost and Management Accounting" profile as a course category. However, each category may have different courses, as for example seminars which can be given inside a subject. For instance, "PhD courses" category contains two courses. The Sicodinet categories are: Cost accounting, Finance Master's Degree, Management Accounting, Managerial Accounting, Accounting Information Systems, Phd Courses, Sanitary Organizations Management, WebQuests Virtual Workshop and Cyber-Factory.

Even though Moodle gives several modular possibilities, we have only included in the initial page two content boards: main menu and courses. In "Main menu" all the interesting links are added. The users usually take part in more than one subject, so they can firstly access to each course from the "Courses" board. Nevertheless, when a user has established his profile, it means that he has checked in the VLS, the courses in which he is participating are showed.

Before accessing to each course, the users can also see some common resources in the Sicodinet initial page: Latest News and Citizen's Charter. News is the main characteristic of a virtual community because it allows sharing interesting information or ideas among users. Sicodinet "Latest News" allows users send news, articles, etc. and teacher can moderate them. Articles and news can be showed in different Sicodinet spaces, depending on their configuration and their time as link. Nevertheless, Moodle allows storing all the news so that every user can access to them. News also may be referred to a specific course or they may be general, so every VLS users can see them. All the users receive general news by means of the "Latest News" forum and, moreover, each subject has its own calendar and specific forums so that users can know specific news of any subject.

Fig. 2. Sicodinet VLS Access page.

4.2 Contents of Each Course

The development of Sicodinet has been carried out by considering students as main actors, that is, “first, students”, in order to promote their activity in the teaching-learning process. Sicodinet includes several areas, which are flexible and easy to access, so that the teaching-learning process can improve its quality by means of ICT and new learning techniques.

All the courses have been designed by using the topic format because it is the format which the teachers follow in the lectures and, the main aim of the VLS is to complete and support them. However, Moodle offers other kind of formats which could be better in other environments or to get other objectives.

The courses have similar formats, although their teachers may use different resources or arrange the information differently, and the initial information is usually the administrative one: timetables, exams, news forums, etc. So, each course has general and specific contents, that is, contents which are in all the courses and own contents.

4.2.1 General Contents

A. People board. It allows accessing to the teachers and other students' information. It has three links which allow seeing teachers and students, making groups and editing the user's personal profile. The teachers of the subject can make student groups' in each course for doing, for example, group tuitions, and the student groups' messages and activities could be visible for other groups (although they can not participate) or they could be only visible for the participants of the specific group.

B. Activities board. The teacher of a course places the most suitable resources, materials and activities for learning each topic. The “Activities” board is a collection of

the contents and activities categories which the course has (questionnaires, forums, glossaries, resources, assignments, etc.). So, the objective is to show a list of the resources which the subject has. Moreover, users can see if they have sent their activities, their marks, etc. This is a very useful board for students because they can check their progress and their marks in every activity.

C. Search Board. It allows look for information from the messages of the forums. It searches all the forums and it does not search the contents or the glossaries.

D. Calendar Board. As we have expounded before, each subject has a calendar which reflects the important activity dates. It makes easy to follow the course. The course events may be programmed by the teachers for a specific course or for all the VLS users. So each user can see the general events of the VLS or the specific events of his course, even he can marks his own important dates.

E. Courses Board. It shows all the courses in which the user is registered (Fig. 3). The user do not have to identify himself again because, as we expounded before, the user only need one user name and one password to access to all his courses.

F. Administration Board. It allows accessing to the management functions of a course and its content is different for teachers and students (Fig. 4). Students only have three options: change their password, their personal activity report and their personal marks. Teachers have more possibilities; they can decide about the resources and activities of their course; they can design the course (name, register period, password, etc); they can see the students' marks; etc.

G. Topic Board. This board facilitates the users to move among the topic of a course and allows accessing to a topic without looking for it in the central part of the page.

H. News Board. It shows the latest messages headline of the "News" forum and facilitates the access to it in order to know their complete content. Moreover, all the participants receive these messages by e-mail.

I. Next events Board. It is related to the calendar and its messages depend on the calendar because this board shows news about dates or deadlines. Is also has links to access to the monthly diary and to introduce a new event.

J. Recent Activity Board. This block presents the changes which have happened since the user's last access, so it offers a quick check about the user's activity and his course friends' work. This board shows the new users, the new components of the course and the new forum messages.

4.2.2 Own Contents of a Course

These contents are set by teachers and depend on the materials which are given to students. These contents are in the central part of the course screen. Each course has several specific contents: curriculum, news forum, methodology, timetables, evaluation, complementary activities, bibliography, exercises, frequently asked questions, evaluation results and wiki. Next, these contents are going to be explained and we will use the "Cost Accounting" course for illustrating them.

Fig. 3. "Courses" Board.

Fig. 4. "Administration" Board.

A. Curriculum. It is a link to the official subject curriculum of the current year, so students are able to get the curriculum by accessing to the course. The central part of the screen has the topics of the current curriculum and users can surf on the specific contents of subject.

B. News Forum. As we showed before, we can set different kind of forum. Each subject has its own forum and all the participants receive its messages because the forum is the main means for communicating news and events. In fact, the news forum works like a notice in which all users can send messages about the VLS, interesting activities, problems, etc. So, the interaction of ICT facilitates the communications among the participants. For example, more than forty five messages have been sent to the "Cost Accounting" forum.

C. Methodology. This section shows the methodology of the lectures; classes, theory and practice, groups, etc. In this section is also set the methodology to follow the subject contents in the VLS.

D. Timetables. This section shows the timetables of the different courses and subject groups, of the exams and it also shows the teachers' tuition hours, which can be face to face or on-line.

E. Evaluation. In this section the evaluation procedure of a subject is shown, as well as the regulations and information about the exams and the exam revisions. We think it is important that students know the evaluation methodology and the current rules for the exam revision which the University and their teachers have decided. Therefore, there is a link to access to the exams regulations.

F. Complementary Activities. This section informs about the activities which are developed during the year and they may be a complement of the main subject, for example seminars, lectures, tutorials, etc. During the last two years the on-line seminar called "Spreadsheets for supporting the management information development" has been performed in the "Cost Accounting" course.

G. Bibliography. This section shows the subject general bibliography, and we specify the basic and the complementary one (which allows studying in depth and increasing the knowledge). Nevertheless, each topic has its own bibliography. For example, there are about 3.500 references in the course "Cost Accounting".

H. Current Year Exercises and Exercise Repository. The exercises wordings of the current year are given so that student can look for them and download them. However, the exercises are also placed in the corresponding topic. Moreover, although the students of "Cost Accounting" have a great number of exercises every year, there is an "Exercise Repository" in every topic which provides exercises wordings and some of their solutions in Excel format. They may be exam exercises or exercises from years before; there are more than 300 exercises which have been developed from year 1991/1992. It is useful because students may do other exercises and check their solutions, apart from the current year exercises which are solved in class. But not all the exercises of the Repository have their solutions because we think students should develop their autonomous learning capacity.

I. Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ's). "Frequently Answers to Questions" are good information sources for users because they show the possible understanding deficiencies in the topics or in their implementations. Sicodinet has a section in which the teachers add the students' general doubts, which may be asked in class, in tuitions or in forums. The FAQ's are grouped in categories, so users can find technical, content or register questions. Moreover, we have developed a glossary with the most frequent questions of each subject so that the search may be easier.

J. Evaluation Results. Sicodinet reflects the marks of the official exams and the marks of the course activities, so the VLS users can know their qualitative and numerical marks.

K. Power Point Summaries. This content is not in all the subjects but it is in the main subject, "Cost Accounting". Every "Cost Accounting" topic has a Power Point summary in order to illustrate the concepts. Developing this content has involved a great effort because there are more than 4.000 slides. These summaries are useful for students because they can revise the topic contents and check their knowledge about the topics.

L. Wiki. Some subjects of the VLS Sicodinet have a wiki which is a complementary tool for developing the course. Specifically, the "Intelligent Management Systems" subject has used this tool because its students are used to work in these environments.

5 Results: What do the users think about Sicodinet?

The Sicodinet project has been an innovation in the traditional methodology which has been used in the University of León because it provides a support for the traditional teaching and improves the quality of the lecture and practise teaching.

Fig. 5. Evaluation of the VLS compared to the traditional learning methods.

We know that the project is not finished because there are always new versions of the Moodle platform and new contents are added, so Sicodinet is always improving and developing. On the other hand, the development of the project depend on the main users' opinion and because of this, we do opinion surveys periodically in order to know what the students think, although they can give their opinion by means of he forums.

As far as students are concerned, there are 110 students who have answered the questionnaire from more than 500 people, that is, the 20% of the registered people. But to sum up the students' evaluation, the Fig. 5 shows the general opinion about Sicodinet. Only one person (0.92%) has declared that the utility of the VLS is "little or null", so we can conclude the result of the project has been very satisfactory for the main users.

6 Conclusions

The ICT have meant a great revolution in the teaching-learning process because standards of education have changed with their use. Nowadays lectures have been sometimes replaced by a virtual relationship among teachers and students. ICT allow the building of knowledge without a face to face meeting. Sicodinet was born to complete lectures and to create a virtual community for building knowledge. Because of this, it is considered as a B-learning experience.

The Sicodinet VLS has been a great innovation compared to the traditional teaching which used to be applied at the University of León and it implied a great effort for its promoters. Nowadays there are other similar initiatives in our University and but when Sicodinet was implanted there were not similar projects. The Sicodinet VLS provides new tools to the teachers and the students. On the one hand, teachers can develop their subjects by using tools which allow add contents but also manage them and their students. On the other hand, students can building their own learning because they can access to information and exchange doubts, ideas, etc. only by using the Internet.

In spite of this project has been developed for three years, we are aware of the project is not finished because we are community which changes constantly; the teachers add new contents, new versions of the Moodle platforms are incorporated and all the users can propose their opinions about the VLS because we are a community which consider all the users' contributions, as we ensure in our Citizen's Charter.

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